

Deliverable D-JRP19-WP1.3

Workpackage WP1.1

Responsible Partner: ISS

Contributing partners: SVA

GENERAL INFORMATION

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1.1. The PARADISE PROJECT

PARADISE (<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-paradise/>) is a multicentre collaborative international project (2020-2022) composed of 15 partners from 12 European countries. PARADISE aims at delivering informative typing schemes and innovative detection strategies applicable to food matrices for both *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia*. Using NGS technologies (genomics and metagenomics), the project will generate much needed data that will enrich our understanding of the epidemiology and genomics of these organisms, and provide the basis on which improved strain-typing schemes will be developed and rigorously tested. In parallel, strategies (nanobodies, aptamers, use of hybridization probes) to enrich for the target pathogens in different matrices will also be developed and tested. Furthermore, PARADISE will engage in multicentre studies to validate the newly developed methods, testing their applicability across the spectrum of relevant matrices in an unprecedented effort at the EU level. These new methodologies will form the basis for integrated approaches aimed at controlling FBPs in the European food chain.

1.2 AGENDA OF THE FINAL (Y5) MEETING HELD on JUNE 22-23, 2022

22 June

9:00-9:30 Coffee

9:30-9:40 Welcome to Uppsala, practical information – [Karin Troell \(SVA\)](#)

9:40-10:10 Parasitic foodborne infections in Europe – [Lucy Robertson \(NMU\)](#)

10:10-10:20 PARADISE until now and forward – [Simone M. Cacciò \(ISS\)](#)

10:20-12:30 **Workpackage 2**

Genomics (Task 2.1)

- *Cryptosporidium parvum* - [Simone M. Cacciò \(ISS\)](#)
- *Giardia duodenalis* assemblage B – [Christian Klotz \(RKI\)](#)

Metagenomics

- (Task 2.2) In silico approaches – [Frits Franssen and Kees van der Ark \(RIVM\)](#)
- (Task 2.3) Experimental approaches – [Paolo Vatta and Simone M. Cacciò \(ISS\)](#)

Discussion on WP2

12:30-13.30 Lunch

13.30-15:00 **Workpackage 3 *Cryptosporidium parvum***

- (Task 3.2) MLST development and Ring Trial – Karin Troell (SVA) and Martha Betson (UoS)
- Optimization and validation of a VNTR typing scheme – Guy Robinson (Cryptosporidium Reference Unit, UK)
- A comparison of typing methods – Karin Troell (SVA)

Discussion

15:00-15:30 Coffee

15.30-16.30 **Workpackage 3 *Giardia duodenalis***

- (Task 2.3) A MLST for *G. duodenalis* assemblage A – Simone M. Cacciò (ISS), Christian Klotz (RKI)
- *G. duodenalis* assemblage B MLST development and Ring Trial – Christian Klotz (RKI)

Discussion

16.30-17:00 Overall Discussion Day 1

19:00- Dinner downtown (paid for by SVA)

23 June

9:00-10:30 **Workpackage 4**

- (Task4.1) State of the art on aptamers – Marco Lalle (ISS) and Gregory Karadjian (ANSES)
- (Task4.1) State of the art on nanobodies - Christian Klotz (RKI)
- (Task4.2) State of the art on capture probes – Kees van der Ark (RIVM), Karin Troell (SVA), Anton de Jong (SVA)

Discussion

10:30-11:00 Coffee

11:00-12:30 General discussion on the project

12:30-13:00 Closure of meeting

13:00-14:0 Lunch

14:00-15:00 Extra time if needed

Major points discussed at the meeting

Comparative genomics (Workpackage 2)

- The presentation reported that the whole genome sequencing effort is essentially complete, and has resulted in sequencing >100 isolates of *C. parvum* and > 30 isolates

of *G. duodenalis* assemblage B. Comparative genomics studies require expertise in bioinformatics that are not readily available within the consortium. Consequently, collaborations were initiated with colleagues at the University of Pavia (the group of Prof. Davide Sasseria for *Cryptosporidium parvum*) and the Charles University of Prague (Dr. Filip Weisz for *Giardia duodenalis* assemblage B).

- There are still samples of *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* that can be sequenced at the whole genome level. A decision was taken to send samples to ANSES in July 2022.
- In terms of publications, efforts will be made to shortly submit a paper on *G. duodenalis* assemblage A, which is almost in its final version. A paper on *C. parvum* comparative genomics should be submitted before the end of 2022, whereas that on *G. duodenalis* comparative genomics paper will probably require more time.

Metagenomics (Workpackage 2)

- There has been good progress regarding the in silico analyses of different metagenomes for detection of foodborne parasites. A paper was published in 2021 by RIVM and ISS, where *Cryptosporidium* was used as a model pathogen to show how sensitivity and specificity of detection vary using different analytical workflows.
- The discussion focused on the results of amplicon-based and shotgun metagenomics for detection of parasites on spiked material. The experiments were designed to explore the limit of detection of the two approaches, using spikes prepared by mixing an excess of plant DNA extracted from a ready-to-eat salad, with DNA from *C. parvum*, *G. duodenalis* and *Toxoplasma gondii*. The amount of parasite DNA was calculated to mimic the low contamination level (10, 50 or 100 oocysts/cysts in a portion, i.e., 30 grams, of ready-to-eat salad) that may occur in natural matrices. As control, species-specific real-time PCR assays were performed at SSI and ISS to confirm that the three parasitic targets could be detected at all spike levels. The amplicon-based platform failed in detecting *G. duodenalis* and *C. parvum*, while *Toxoplasma gondii* was detected in two of the three spikes (100 and 50 oocysts). The shotgun metagenomics analyses revealed that many sequences initially attributed to parasites were actually of plant origin, as demonstrated by a systematic BLAST approach.
- To further explore the issue, a suggestion was made to prepare new spikes with a wider range of contamination levels, including higher parasite-to-plant DNA ratio. ISS offered to prepare the new set of spikes for *C. parvum*, and to apply shotgun metagenomics to these samples before the end of August. It was also discussed to involve SSI in order to run the amplicon-based platform on the new panel of spiked samples.
- The impact of the sequencing platform used was also discussed. On the one hand, it was mentioned that the MiSeq Illumina platform can generate longer reads (250 bp), which may decrease the observed spurious matches against the matrix (plant), but at the cost of total base output. On the other hand, the HiSeq Illumina platform has higher output but shorter reads (150 bp).
- Finally, the possibility to create in silico spikes with different backgrounds of mock populations was discussed, as a way to explore the impact of the matrix on the detection of parasites. Karin Troell (SVA) was able to get access to data from water samples spiked with mock communities including *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia*, which have been uploaded in the Paradise cloud space and therefore made available for analyses.

New MLST, SOP and interlaboratory comparison (Workpackage 3)

- The in silico selection of markers has been completed, and laboratory tests have verified the amplificability of the markers and the possibility of obtaining clean, interpretable Sanger sequences for *C. parvum* (ISS, SVA) and *G. duodenalis* (RKI). From this, new MLST schemes have been developed and tested on an informative panel of samples collected by the consortium. This has allowed a robust validation of the schemes, and an evaluation of their discriminatory power. Work is also ongoing to compare the MLST and the MLVA schemes for *C. parvum*.
- SOPs were prepared by the partners in charge (ISS for *C. parvum*, RKI for *G. duodenalis* assemblage B) and distributed to all partners during spring 2022. Webinars were organized to present the typing schemes to all partners and to provide tutorials for the analyses and interpretation of Sanger sequencing data.
- Inter-laboratory comparison tests (BFR in charge) were performed during May/June 2022 and involved all partners. The first results from the *G. duodenalis* Assemblage B MLST ring trial were presented at the meeting. It was underlined that the different results obtained by partners were likely related to differences in handling and interpreting the sequence data rather than representing technical issues. The importance of conducting full analysis of the data, including identification of positions showing allelic sequence heterozygosity (ASH), was stressed. For the *C. parvum* MLST ring test, a few partners were late in providing the results, but the overall analysis should be completed by the end of August.
- The discussion then focused on dissemination of the results. It was agreed that Karin Troell (SVA) will be responsible for two papers, one on the new *C. parvum* MLST, and the second on a comparison between typing methods (MLST, VNTR and *gp60*). Christian Klotz (RKI) will be responsible for papers on MLST schemes for *G. duodenalis* assemblage A and B. The importance of paper submission before the end of the project was stressed. The pipeline developed for the analyses of *G. duodenalis* assemblage B genomes, and then for the design of the MLST scheme, should also be published (RKI).
- A short discussion centered on criteria for inclusion of partners in publications from the project. It was decided that all partners who provided samples and/or contributed to the analyses of data and preparation of manuscripts will be included among the authors.

Aptamers (Workpackage 4)

- Selection of aptamers has been completed for both *G. duodenalis* (ANSES and ISS) and *C. parvum* (ANSES). Synthesis of conjugated aptamers (either with biotin or FITC) has been completed and the partners in charge (ANSES and ISS) have evaluated aptamer binding to *Giardia* cysts by several approaches (IFA, ELISA) and are expected to run other assays (e.g., flow cytometry). Aptamer testing for *Cryptosporidium* oocysts is in progress at ANSES. So far, none of the aptamers tested showed specificity for the cyst wall, whereas a weak signal was observed inside the cyst. Drafting of a SOP and organization of the ring trial, as originally planned, might be not feasible due to time constraints.
- As aptamer development is a slow process, and the time remaining is not sufficient to start it all over again, the possibility to collaborate with and test candidate material developed by other research groups will be explored at the upcoming ICOPA meeting (Copenhagen, 21-26 August). The results from the PARADISE project will be presented at this important conference.

Nanobodies (Workpackage 4)

- The presentation from the partner in charge (RKI) showed the progress and challenges experienced during the selection of nanobodies against *G. duodenalis* and *C. parvum* (oo)cysts. At present, 10 positive candidate clones against *G. duodenalis* cysts have been selected, while no good candidates could be selected for *C. parvum*. Immunofluorescence and flow cytometry tests will be used to further evaluate the properties of the selected nanobodies against *G. duodenalis* cysts. Nanobodies will be biotinylated and attached to magnetic beads, and an assay to capture the target (*G. duodenalis* cysts) will be performed.
- It was agreed that the two candidate nanobodies for *G. duodenalis* can be tested by other partners (ISS, SVA, ANSES, PIWET, NMU, possibly RIVM) before the end of the project, to provide additional data.

Capture probes (Workpackage 4)

- The presentation from the partners in charge (RIVM, SVA) reported that, due to delay in results from WP3 on new markers, a decision was taken to focus on the magnetic capture hybridization probes developed during Y1 in PARADISE, and generate more data on their applicability. Extensive laboratory tests at SVA and RIVM allowed validation of two *C. parvum* markers (18S and *gp60* genes) and SOPs will be prepared based on these results. An inter-laboratory test will be organized to involve partners that have agreed to participate (RKI, ANSES, VRI, FOHM, SLV, INIAV). It was stressed, however, that all partners that got funding from the project for this task should be involved. SVA and RIVM will share the protocol and send the samples. The planned training has not been performed yet, due to travel constraints during the pandemic.

Other notes

- The project will finish at the end of 2022. It was recalled that the final report should be drafted in November and completed before December.
- Data management plan needs to be updated before the end of September.

1.3 LIST of PARTICIPANTS

Funded partners

<u>INSTITUTE</u>	<u>NAME and SURNAME</u>	<u>COUNTRY</u>
ANSES	Yannick Blanchard Gregory Karadjan Karim Adjou	France
ISS	Simone M. Cacciò Marco Lalle Paolo Vatta	Italy
NVI	Sokratis Ptochos	Norway
PHA	Ioana Bujila Gustav Killander	Sweden
PIWET	Jacek Sroka Maciek Kochanowski	Poland

RIVM	Frits Franssen Kees van der Ark	The Netherlands
RKI	Christian Klotz	Germany
SLV	Hilde Riedel	Sweden
SVA	Karin Troell Emma Östlund Anton de Jong Harri Ahola Lauren Davies	Sweden
UoS	Martha Benson	United Kingdom

Associated partners

<u>INSTITUTE</u>	<u>NAME and SURNAME</u>	<u>COUNTRY</u>
CRU	Guy Robinson	United Kingdom
NMU	Lucy Robertson	Norway

Picture of the participants at the final meeting of the PARADISE project organized by SVA in Uppsala, Sweden on 22-23 June 2022.

